

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DAVIS****FIRST NAME: CYNTHIA****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What are the ideas of conversing with your readers?

- To explore the type of story sought through factual contextualized questions.
- The reading experience conversation goes beyond supplying reading and other leisure suggestions to readers and seeks to understand the desired reading experience holistically.

- When you read a book or an article or report, you silently converse with its authors- and through them with everyone else they have read.¹**
- When anyone—students or scientists—conducts research, they are reading and interpreting the information that analyzes the topic—a topic that has been discussed, perhaps for decades.

2. What are the different types of research?

- The Qualitative vs. Quantitative act will consider data in the form of words for quantitative data; it can use statistical analysis methods to test relationships between variables. Qualitative data can use methods such as thematic analysis to interpret patterns and meanings in the data.
- The position taken in this book is that quantitative and qualitative research methods can be appropriately integrated to make distinct and substantive contributions to knowledge.²**
- The Quantitative studies rely on numerical or measurable data. In contrast, qualitative studies rely on personal accounts or documents that

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 22.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 6.

illustrate in detail how people think or respond within society. Quantitative Research. Quantitative studies, in contrast, require different data collection methods

- They are Quantitative and Qualitative Research.

3. **Describe the potential for research bias.**

- To address bias linked to prior knowledge of the data and address difficulties arising from reduced analytic flexibility in pre-registration
- Both quantitative and qualitative researchers acknowledge that the potential for bias exists in research. However, quantitative and qualitative researchers often take different positions on the likelihood of bias impacting their research.³**
- To help ensure that pre-registered analyses will be appropriate for the data.
- To enable pre-registration of non-hypothesis-driven research. The scope for these biases to distort research outputs from secondary data analysis is perhaps particularly acute.

4. **How to research concept contribute to subainable development?**

³ Turabian, 15.

- The concept of research in sustainability builds on the efficient use of locally available resources and on the use of adapted technologies
- The invention of research is a major source of development, especially the aspect of modern technology.⁴**
- The importance of the research industry for the three elements of sustainable development, namely economic growth, social progress, and effective protection of the environment, cannot be disregarded.
- To accept the premise that ‘the purpose of management is to serve human needs’ and management's broad purpose today is the achievement of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, research is at the center.

5. **How to read generously to understand and critically to engage?**

- To read critically, students need to move beyond reading just for content—the way students typically read in high school—and instead read in a way that goes deeper, addressing questions such as: What was the author's purpose? Who was the intended audience? Who or what was the author responding to?

⁴ Ibid., 22.

- To start, read promising sources twice. First, read generously. Pay attention to what sparks your interest. Reread passages that puzzle or confuse you.
- A reading comparison of published statements about the source-use skills of sophomores in the 1990s and those revealed by the more recent.
- Then, if a source seems important or challenges your own position, read it a second time slowly and more critically. When you read a passage, think not only about what it says but about how you would respond. Record those responses in your notes or—if you own the source or a copy of it—in the margins of the source.⁵**

6. **What is a parenthetical citations?**

- The Parenthetical citations are useful because they give credit to the original author or speaker's message or research within the text
- Parenthetical citations include enough information for readers to find the full citation in your citing a specific passage), a page number or other locating information.⁶**

⁵ Ibid., 45.

⁶ Turabian, 239.

- In parenthetical format, citations include all relevant information (author's last name, publication year, page number).
- Parenthetical citations are used in MLA format and closely resemble those in APA format. However, there are two main differences between MLA and APA formats. In narrative citation format, the author of the cited work is referenced as part of the written sentence itself.

7. **What is the nature of dissertation research?**

- The scope can be extensive or at least apply to a realistic community or geographical area. Analysis of data will require sophisticated analytical processes. Recognized research approaches, methods, and paradigms should be used. The report should be 30,000 to 70,000 words in length.
- In the case of doctoral studies, your research design will probably move from underlying philosophical assumptions and theoretical knowledge to new knowledge and a solution to a problem.
- A doctoral dissertation research design will probably move from underlying philosophical assumptions and theoretical knowledge to new knowledge and a solution to a problem.

Dissertation research is a collaborative process primarily involving students and their major professors with additional input and evaluation provided by the supervisory committee.⁷

8. **What is the function of European Economic and Social Committee?**

To Promote the values of European integration and advance the cause of participatory democracy and civil society organizations

Promote a participatory EU by giving workers' and employers' organizations and other interest groups a voice and securing dialogue with them.

The Economic and Social Committee is governed by Articles 300 to 304 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. Its three key tasks are to: ensure that EU policy and law are geared to economic and social conditions, by seeking a consensus that serves the common good. promote a participatory EU by giving workers' and employers' organizations and other interest groups a voice and securing dialogue with them.⁸

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Commission 2021), 96-97.

- Ensure that EU policy and law are geared to economic and social conditions, by seeking a consensus that serves the common good.

9. **What is the importance of the European Economic Budget to the EU population**

- The budget of the European Union is used to finance EU funding programs (such as the European Regional Development Fund, the Cohesion Fund, Horizon Europe, or Erasmus+) and other expenditures at the European level. The EU budget is primarily an investment budget.
- It aims to complement national budgets. Its purpose is to implement the priorities that all EU members have agreed upon.
- It provides European added value by supporting actions that, in line with the principle of subsidiarity and proportionality, can be more effective than actions taken at the national, regional, or local levels.
- The General Budget of the European Union, which does not include the European Development Fund (see 22.11), is often simply called the budget (note lower case).⁹**

⁹ Ibid., 96–97.

10. What is research?

- Research is also a careful consideration of study regarding a particular concern or research problem using scientific methods.
- Research encourages you to find the most recent information available; research gives additional value. The research helps you narrow your scope, research teaches you better discernment and advance trends.
- The main purpose is to discover various facts and their interrelationship and to help us discard distortions and contribute to our understanding of reality.
- In this book, we use research in a specific way to mean a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher but also others want to solve. Research thus includes the steps involved in presenting or reporting it.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Turabian, 19.

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